

Occurrence of Aflatoxins B₁ in Some Spices and Grains Sold in Some Markets in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Food is a very important aspect of human life and its safety is a priority if the health of the people is to be assured. Aflatoxins is a public health problem in Nigeria being it carcinogenic, risk assessment, monitoring, quality control and empirical data were needed. To determine aflatoxins B₁ in the food the ELISA method was used. The range of aflatoxins B₁ concentration in analyzed samples are; garlic cloves (0.30 ± 0.25 – 6.37 ± 0.12 ppb), bitter kola (2.27 ± 0.17 – 13.33 ± 0.09 ppb), moringa leaves (4.19. ± 0.06 – 9.26 ± 0.12 ppb), ginger rhizomes (0.43 ± 0.23 – 6.43 ± 0.33 ppb), zobo rose bulbs (3.40 ± 0.00 – 19.43 ± 0.07 ppb), groundnut seeds (ND – 7.43 ± 0.07 ppb), white maize seeds (0.43 ± 0.23 – 22.70 ± 0.00 ppb), white bean seeds (6.40 ± 0.00 – 19.26 ± 0.12 ppb), soya bean seeds (1.47 ± 0.26 – 4.16 ± 0.09 ppb), red guinea corn seeds (2.00 ± 0.00 – 5.13 ± 0.07), local white rice seeds (ND - 6.80 ± 0.00), millet seeds (6.66 ± 0.30 – 8.83 ± 0.03). The highest and lowest concentrations were from 22.70 ± 0.00 ppb to 0.30 ± 0.25 ppb with highest concentration in white rice and lowest in garlic cloves both from Tsafe Market. And 34 (94.4 %) out of 36 analyzed samples, 23(63.9 %) were exceeded permissible limit of 4 ppb set by WHO, NAFDAC and SON.

Keywords: Contamination, Incidence, Aflatoxins B₁, Market, Grains; ELISA, Health, SON

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Introduction

Aflatoxins are produced on various herbal remedies, grains and nuts, e.g. garlic, ginger, corn, fruits, dried fruits and etc in the field and during storage. Aflatoxins occur mainly in hot and humid regions where high temperature and humidity are optimal for molds growth and toxins production (Ventura *et al.*, 2022; Zollner and Mayer–Helm, 2020). Its presence is enhanced by factors such as stress or damage to the plants due to drought before harvest, insect-activity, soil type and inadequate storage conditions (Alcaide-Molina *et al.*, 2019). The Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) has set a 4 µg/kg for aflatoxins B₁ (SON, 2021) (SON, 2010), 20 µg/kg for total Aflatoxins (SON, 2010) and 4 µg/kg standards for maximum total aflatoxin concentrations for maize, raw groundnuts and groundnut cake (Kuli-Kuli) (SON, 2008). There are basically four types of aflatoxins B₁, B₂, G₁ and G₂. Its order of toxicity is B₁>G₁>B₂>G₂ (Ali *et al.*, 2020, Alcaide-Molina *et al.*, 2019).

Aflatoxins are potent carcinogens and may affect all organs systems, especially the liver and kidneys; they cause liver cancer, and have been linked to other types of cancer-AFB₁ is known to be carcinogenic in humans; the potency of aflatoxin to cause liver cancer is significantly enhanced in the presence of infection with hepatitis B virus (HBV);

- i. Aflatoxins are mutagenic in bacteria (affect the DNA), genotoxic, and have the potential to cause birth defects in children;
- ii. Children may become stunted, although these data have yet to be confirmed because other factors also contribute to growth faltering e.g. low socioeconomic status, chronic diarrhea, infectious diseases, malnutrition;
- iii. Aflatoxins cause immune-suppression, therefore may decrease resistance to infectious agents (e.g. HIV, Tuberculosis) (WHO, 2018).

Mycotoxins comprise four main group, namely aflatoxins, ochratoxins, fumonisins and tricothecenes, all of which have toxic effects. Aflatoxins have been extensively studied and are classified as group 1 human carcinogens by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC, 1993).

Equally, groundnut and its products are confirmed to be easily contaminated by aflatoxins B₁ and B₂ commonly produced by *aspergillus*. It was reported during the study that samples were collected from different traders (big, medium and small). To have a more reliable result regarding the present of the aflatoxins in the products, the researchers collected products of the two different farming seasons – dry and rainy. Aflatoxin B₁ was detected in 8 of 15 samples collected during the rainy season, and in 5 samples collected during the dry season; aflatoxins B₂ was detected in some samples contaminated with aflatoxin B₁. (Haryad and Setiastuty, 2022).

Furthermore, another study was carried out on 1029 samples of brown rice, 1561 samples of white rice, 33 samples of broken rice, 13 samples of sella rice and 52 samples of parboiled rice exported from Pakistan between 2006 – 2010 for qualitative analysis of aflatoxin B₁, B₂, G₁ and G₂ by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). 350 (22.42 %) samples of brown rice, 341 (33.13 %) samples of white rice, 13 (39.39 %) samples of broken rice, 25 (24.27 %) samples of sella rice and 14 (26.92 %) samples of parboiled rice were found contaminated with B₁; B₂ was detected in 57 (3.65 %) samples of brown rice, 33 (3.20 %) samples of white rice and 1 (3.03 %) samples of broken rice while G₁ was equally detected in 57 (3.65 %) samples of brown rice, 9 (0.8 %) samples of white rice, 1 (1.5 %) samples of parboiled rice and G₂ was absent in all the samples (Nisa *et al.*, 2020).

Materials and Method

Methonolanalar; distilled water; aflatoxins test kit; Stat fax ELISA reader; Aflatoxin Standards; weighing balance; blender; micro pipette; microtitre wells and buffer solution.

Sample Collection

Samples of garlic cloves, bitter kola seeds, moringa leaves, ginger rhizomes, zobo rose bulbs, groundnut seeds, white maize seeds, white beans seeds, soya beans seeds, red guinea corn seeds, local white rice seeds and millet seeds were procured from three different markets: Tsafe, Shinkafi and Talata Mafara in Zamfara State. Samples were procured from the respective markets on the market days, repeatedly for three weeks. Then corresponding samples from each market were harmonized to make representative samples of each. Twelve representative samples were made from each market making a total of 36 samples.

Sample Extraction

Exactly 2.0 g of pretreated sample was added into a sample bottle and 10 ml of 70% methanol was added. The mixture was shaken for 10 minutes using a multi-shaker. After through mixing, the mixture was then filtered. Exactly 100 µl of the filtrate was added to 600 µl distilled water in a test tube. Then 50 µl of the diluted filtrate was added into micro titre well in the test.

Quantitative Analysis (RIDASCREEN[®] Aflatoxin ELISA Test kit)

The basis of the test is the antigen-antibody reaction. The wells in the microtitre strips are coated with captured antibodies directed against anti-aflatoxin antibodies. Standards or the sample solutions,

aflatoxin-enzyme conjugate and anti-aflatoxin antibodies were added. Free and enzyme conjugated aflatoxin compete for the aflatoxin antibody binding sites (competitive enzyme immunoassay). At the same time, the anti-aflatoxin antibodies are also bound by the immobilized capture antibodies. Any unbound enzyme conjugate was then removed in a washing step. Then substrate / chromogen solution was added to the wells and incubated. Bound enzyme conjugate converted the chromogen into a blue product. The addition of the stop solution (1M HCl) leads to a color change from blue to yellow. The measurement was performed photometrically at 450 nm. (RIDA SCREEN[®] Aflatoxin ELISA test kits, 2019).

Note: When the antigen level in the sample is high, the level of antibody-bound enzyme-labeled antigen is lower and the color is lighter. Conversely, when the antigen level in the sample is low, the level of antibody-bound enzyme-labeled antigen is higher and the color is darker. (MBL, 2019).

Quantitative Analysis (Stat fax ELISA Reader)

A source of continuous radiation over the wavelength from the source spectrum. A Monochromator selected 450 nm band of wavelength from the source spectrum. A detector converted radiant energy to electrical energy. Read out device read and responded to the detector.

Results and Discussion

The outcomes of the qualitative analysis for aflatoxins B₁ of the analyzed samples from Tsafe, Shinkafi and Talata Mafara Markets in Zamfara State are appeared in Table 1. Presence and absence of aflatoxins were indicated with plus (+) and minus (-) signs respectively. The result indicated presence of aflatoxins B₁ in all the samples except Talata Mafara market groundnut and white rice samples. This observation may be due to experimental error or samples were new to the market not exposed to storage factors that promote proliferation of aflatoxins. (Haruna, *et al.*, 2017).

The concentrations range of aflatoxins B₁ were appeared in Table 2. The concentration range of aflatoxins B₁ in all the analyzed samples were 22.70 – 0.30 ppb, with the highest concentration in Tsafe market white rice and lowest concentration in garlic cloves from the same market.

Table: 1 Result of Qualitative Analysis of Aflatoxins in Samples

S/No	Sample names	Tsafe Market 1	Shinkafi Marker 2	T/Mafara Market 3
		AF B ₁	AF B ₁	AF B ₁
1.	Garlic cloves	+	+	+
2.	Bitter kola seeds	+	+	+
3.	Moringa leaves	+	+	+
4.	Ginger Rhizomes	+	+	+
5.	Zobo rose bulbs	+	+	+
6.	Groundnut seeds	+	+	-
7.	White Maize seeds	+	+	+
8.	White Bean seeds	+	+	+
9.	Soya bean seeds	+	+	+
10.	Red Guinea corn seeds	+	+	+
11.	Local white rice seeds	+	+	-
12.	Millet seeds	+	+	+

Key: + Means Aflatoxins Presence and – Means Aflatoxins Absence

Table: 2. Average Concentration of Aflatoxin B₁

Sample Names	Average concentration of Aflatoxin B ₁ (ppb)		
	Tsafe Market 1	Shinkafi Market 2	T/Mafara Market 3
Garlic cloves	0.30±0.25	2.36±0.27	6.37±0.12
Bitter kola seeds	2.27±0.17	7.73±0.17	13.33±0.09
Moringa leaves	4.33±0.24	4.19±0.06	9.26±0.12
Ginger Rhizomes	0.43±0.23	6.26±0.418	6.43±0.33
Zobo rose bulbs	19.36±0.23	3.40±0.00	19.43±0.07
Groundnut seeds	2.13±0.07	7.43±0.07	ND
White Maize seeds	22.70±0.00	4.66±0.15	0.43±0.23
White Bean seeds	7.63±0.12	19.26±0.12	6.40±0.00
Soya bean seeds	2.10±0.10	1.47±0.26	4.16±0.09
Red Guinea corn seeds	4.33±0.13	5.13±0.07	2.00±0.00
Local white rice seeds	0.43±0.23	6.80±0.00	ND
Millet seeds	6.70±0.20	6.60±0.30	8.83±0.03
Standard Organization	WHO,SON and NAFDAC	Aflatoxins B ₁ permissible limit 4 ppb	

Discussion

The incidence of aflatoxins B₁ showed in almost all the samples analyzed, 34 (94.4 %) out of 36 samples were found to be contaminated. And 23 (63.9 %) were exceeded permissible limits of 4 ppb set by WHO, SON, and NAFDAC. The concentration range from 22.70 ± 0.00 ppb to 0.30 ± 0.25 was indicated in all the samples. This study was in agreement with Felagha, *et al.*, (2006), the mean total aflatoxins concentration range from 1.73 ± 0.09 to 37.23 ± 3.66 µg / kg which is also in agreement with that of Haruna, *et al.*, (2017) who reported that aflatoxins was indicated in 4 out of 14 spices (28.6 %) namely African nutmeg (17.2 µg / kg) and chilies (16.6 µg / kg) were exceeded acceptable limit. And also agreed with Batagarawa *et al.*, (2015), reported 73.3 % of the feeds and feed ingredients were contaminated with aflatoxins, among the 14 grains samples analyzed, 12 were contaminated (85.7 % incidence).

Conclusion

Out of 36 samples analyzed 34(94.4 %) were found contaminated with aflatoxins B₁ and 23 (63.9%) were above permissible limit of 4 ppb set by WHO, SON, and NAFDAC. The concentration range started from 27.70 ± 0.00 ppb to 0.03 ± 0.25 was indicated in all the analyzed samples.

Recommendation

An aflatoxins resistance varieties of food stuffs need to be produced, good storage practices are needed to prevent aflatoxins contamination and an epidemiological study need to be conducted to fully understand the dangers associated with high aflatoxins presence in foodstuffs in Nigeria.

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